

Beyond the Chatbot: What Brain Science Tells Us About AI's Future

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 3-minute video overview: <https://share.descript.com/view/kz2d14mrd2u>

Abstract

Artificial intelligence is moving beyond the chatbot phase. Current large language models (LLMs) are highly fluent and often useful, yet they remain constrained by weak grounding, unreliable factuality, and a mode of operation that relies largely on pattern prediction rather than robust understanding. This paper argues that the next major step in AI is more likely to come from systems that build richer models of the world and incorporate principles from brain science, especially the integration of perception, memory, emotion, prediction, and adaptive control. Drawing on Evian Gordon's total brain framework for Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), Yann LeCun's world-model approach, and the author's work on AI in education, the paper argues that future AI should be judged not only by performance but also by its implications for human learning and development. The educational question is therefore not simply how capable AI becomes, but whether its design and use support or erode the cognitive processes on which human expertise depends.

1. The LLM Moment: Capability and Constraint

Generative AI is now embedded in study, work, and public communication. Students and educators use chatbots to brainstorm, summarise, draft, and refine text, and these uses can provide genuine support, particularly for learners with language-based difficulties (Purnell, 2026a). Yet the same systems also raise structural concerns that become especially salient when viewed through the lens of educational neuroscience.

1.1 Cognitive debt

The most serious educational risk is cognitive offloading: the transfer of mental work to a tool that reduces the learner's effortful processing. Early electroencephalography (EEG), which records the brain's electrical activity from large groups of neurons, suggests that students who use conversational AI for essay writing show reduced connectivity in networks linked to active composition and may struggle to recall details from their own submitted work soon afterwards (Kosmyna et al., 2025). These findings are preliminary, but they align with a substantial body of research on learning, which shows that durable knowledge depends on retrieval, active processing, and repeated use of working memory over time (Cowan, 2014; Purnell et al., 1991; Sweller, 1994).

When AI performs the integrative work learners need to practise for themselves, students may feel efficient without building the long-term neural schemas that underpin expertise (Cowan, 2014; Sweller, 1994). The issue is therefore not convenience alone. It is that routine reliance on AI may reduce the very cognitive activity that learning requires.

1.2 Hallucination and misplaced trust

A second structural problem is hallucination. LLMs can produce fluent but false claims, fabricated references, and invented evidence because they are not designed to verify facts as they generate outputs (McKenna et al., 2023; Shao, 2025). Benchmarks and external testing indicate that factual errors remain common enough to be treated as a design limitation rather than an occasional anomaly (Gaudiaut, 2025; Google FACTS Team, 2025; Mims, 2026).

In education, the problem is compounded by style. AI output often appears authoritative even when it is wrong, and learners with limited prior knowledge are least able to detect those errors (Purnell, 2026a). Verification must therefore be treated as a core academic practice, especially given that fabricated or inaccurate citations remain a live problem in research-facing uses of general-purpose models (Aydin et al., 2026).

1.3 Prediction without grounded understanding

These limitations reflect how current LLMs operate. At their core, they are advanced next-token prediction systems trained on vast text corpora. They produce statistically plausible sequences rather than knowledge grounded in an internal model of the world (Purnell, 2026a). This helps explain their uneven performance across tasks, a pattern described by Google DeepMind as ‘jagged intelligence’ (Achiam et al., 2023; Burnell et al., 2026).

The contrast with human development is instructive. Children learn through embodied experience of space, time, causality, and social interaction, whereas LLMs learn from static text detached from action and consequence (LeCun, 2022; LeCun, 2024). This gap helps explain both their strengths and their current limitations.

2. What Current AI Lacks

A growing body of work in neuroscience and AI suggests that simply scaling current large language models will not yield human-level general intelligence (Gordon et al., 2026; LeCun, 2022; Metz, 2026). The limitation is not a lack of capability. Instead, key features underpinning human intelligence, such as flexibility, transfer, and resilience, remain absent.

2.1 Gordon’s total brain framework

Gordon and colleagues propose that AGI development and evaluation should be informed by evidence on whole-brain function, extending beyond performance on isolated tasks (Gordon et al., 2026). Their framework draws on the Total Brain International Database, which integrates large-scale neural, physiological, and behavioural data across the lifespan and across clinical and non-clinical populations, encompassing 7 billion data points from more than 500,000 individuals and over 300 peer-reviewed publications (Gordon et al., 2026). This perspective treats intelligence as an emergent property of interacting systems spanning cognition, emotion, and the continuum from unconscious to conscious processing over time (Gordon et al., 2026).

This matters because human intelligence is not merely a set of separable abilities. Effective performance depends not only on memory, reasoning, and attention in isolation, but also on how these processes are coordinated, regulated, and adapted to changing conditions. Within this framework, emotion is not peripheral. It serves as a core guidance mechanism, directing attention, assigning value, and shaping action in concert with cognitive processes (Bechara & Damasio, 2005; Gordon et al., 2008; Tyng et al., 2017).

2.2 Emotion and unconscious regulation

This point is important because modern cognitive neuroscience no longer treats emotion and reason as opposites. Emotional signals help the brain register what is important, focus attention, and support working memory, while unconscious processes contribute to rapid evaluation and learned response patterns (Bechara & Damasio, 2005; Kahneman, 2011; Tyng et al., 2017). In everyday terms, human thinking works in part because much of its guidance system operates below full awareness.

If future AI systems overlook these regulatory functions, they risk missing a core basis for how human cognition adapts to uncertainty and change. Emerging interpretability research suggests that

large language models may develop internal, emotion-like representations that shape their outputs, although their nature and status remain unsettled (Sofroniew et al., 2026). The point is not that current AI systems feel in any human sense. Rather, control processes analogous to affect may have computational value, reinforcing the view that emotion–cognition dynamics are central, not peripheral, to intelligent behaviour.

2.3 LeCun’s world-model approach

LeCun arrives at a similar conclusion from a different direction. He argues that current LLMs are unlikely to reach human-level intelligence because they rely on pattern prediction without grounded world models, persistent memory, or robust planning mechanisms (LeCun, 2022). His proposed alternative is a family of architectures centred on predictive world models: systems that learn representations of how the world changes over time and use those representations to guide reasoning, planning, and action.

The appeal of this approach is that it moves AI beyond surface-level completion towards modelling the world’s structure and dynamics. Rather than asking a system merely to continue a sequence of words, it asks the system to form expectations about objects, events, and consequences. In this respect, LeCun’s proposal broadly aligns with the wider neuroscientific view that intelligence depends on memory, prediction, control, and learning through interaction with a changing world (Gordon et al., 2026; LeCun, 2022). Taken together, Gordon and LeCun suggest that more general AI will require richer, more grounded internal models, not merely larger language models.

3. What a More Brain-Aligned AI Would Look Like

If these critiques are correct, future AI is likely to be hybrid rather than purely language-based. More capable systems would need internal models of objects, events, and causal relations, along with mechanisms for memory, planning, and assigning significance under uncertainty that function more like regulation than simple output ranking (Gordon et al., 2026; LeCun, 2022). They would also need to move beyond jagged competence towards broader transfer across unfamiliar tasks.

Current evidence suggests this gap remains substantial. Chollet’s ARC framework defines general intelligence as the efficient acquisition of new skills from limited information. The latest ARC-AGI-3 benchmark continues to show a large gap between human performance and frontier systems in novel interactive environments (ARC Prize Foundation, 2026; Chollet, 2019). The implication is not that progress is trivial, but that strong language performance should not be mistaken for general intelligence.

This has educational importance because the systems entering classrooms are likely to become more context-aware, multimodal, and adaptive before they are broadly reliable in a human sense. Educational institutions, therefore, face a moving target: AI will become more persuasive and more deeply embedded even as core questions about grounding, generalisation, and alignment remain unresolved.

4. Educational Risks in a More Capable AI Era

More capable AI could exacerbate existing educational problems rather than automatically solve them. Four issues warrant particular attention.

4.1 Deepening cognitive debt

As AI becomes more personalised and better at anticipating learner needs, cognitive offloading may become less visible yet more seductive. A system that tracks a learner's history, identifies areas of difficulty, and provides just-in-time support may appear highly effective, particularly for students with attention, memory, or language difficulties (Purnell, 2026a). Yet if that support routinely

replaces retrieval, planning, and explanation, it risks undermining the practice through which those abilities develop.

The concern is not assistance itself. It is the possibility that AI becomes a permanent cognitive prosthesis rather than a scaffold, leaving students able to complete tasks without consolidating the knowledge and strategies underpinning independent performance (Cowan, 2014; Kosmyna et al., 2025; Purnell, 2026a; Sweller, 1994).

4.2 Trust, accountability, and infrastructure

More complex systems will also be harder to interpret. If future AI tools encode assumptions about risk, behaviour, and value in opaque internal models, bias may become more difficult to detect and to explain to educators, students, and institutions (Sofroniew et al., 2026). Professional accountability will depend not only on whether systems work, but also on whether their recommendations can be interrogated and justified.

A related issue is infrastructure dependence. AI deployment relies on expensive, resource-intensive technical systems shaped by computing constraints, commercial pressures, and substantial energy use (Field, 2026; Oviedo et al., 2026; Sor, 2026). In education, reliability and sustainability are not peripheral concerns. They are integral to the governance problem.

4.3 Cognitive vulnerability

Well-designed AI may offer real benefits for learners with cognitive or mental health challenges through adaptive pacing, multimodal explanations, and personalised support (Purnell, 2026a). At the same time, there is a risk that such systems replace rather than support the development of retrieval, planning, and organisational skills. Direct evidence for these populations remains limited, so caution is warranted.

The broader issue is that the learners who stand to benefit most from support may also be the most vulnerable if that support becomes dependency. Educational design must therefore distinguish between scaffolding that builds future capability and substitution that conceals its absence.

4.4 Assessment integrity

Assessment is where cognitive offloading is most visible. AI-enabled smart glasses and related wearable systems can now provide covert, real-time assistance that blurs the boundary between individual performance and networked support (BBC News, 2026; Purnell, 2026b). When this becomes feasible at scale, qualifications risk becoming weaker signals of what a learner can actually do.

The likely answer is not endless surveillance. It is assessment design that makes thinking visible through oral explanation, staged production, contextual application, and other forms of evidence that are harder to outsource covertly (Purnell, 2026b).

5. Educational Response

The answer is neither uncritical enthusiasm nor outright bans. The real task is to guide how AI is used so that it strengthens learning rather than replacing the thinking that education is meant to build.

5.1 AI literacy

Students and educators need explicit AI literacy that explains how current systems generate outputs, why hallucinations occur, and why verification matters. They also need practical habits of use that position AI as a tool for questioning, drafting, and critique rather than as a substitute for understanding (Aydin et al., 2026; Purnell, 2026a; Purnell, 2026c). Emerging initiatives, such as

Estonia's AI Leap program, illustrate a system-level effort to orient AI use towards addressing challenges rather than towards passive consumption of answers, although independent evaluation remains limited (Earp, 2025).

5.2 Brain-aligned design and governance

Institutions should evaluate AI not only for immediate task performance but also for its effects on attention, memory, emotion regulation, and long-term learning (Gordon et al., 2026; Purnell, 2026a). In practice, this favours tools that support retrieval practice, spacing, elaboration, and access to trusted course materials over systems that merely generate polished responses (Sweller, 1994).

Governance must also address data use. Educational institutions need clear oversight of which learner data are transmitted, how long they are retained, whether they are used to train or improve commercial models, and what meaningful rights students have to refuse, limit, or review such uses (Purnell, 2026a). Pedagogy and governance are distinct responsibilities, yet both are central to the responsible adoption of AI.

5.3 Engaging sceptics

Scepticism about AI is often grounded in legitimate concerns about surveillance, bias, environmental costs, labour displacement, and the concentration of power among large technology firms (Purnell, 2026a; Roberts, 2026). In some settings, this unease is hardening into broader social resistance, and recent reporting indicates that hostility towards AI infrastructure and its public advocates has, in isolated cases, escalated beyond criticism and protest into vandalism and violence (Lopez, 2026; Nolan, 2026). This climate has also been intensified by high-profile claims from technology leaders and investors that emphasise labour replacement, post-work futures, and the redundancy of human effort, even though current evidence suggests a more mixed picture, with many organisations reporting limited measurable gains from AI adoption and labour-market analyses indicating more job reshaping and augmentation than large-scale displacement (Anthropic, 2026; Boston Consulting Group, 2026; PwC, 2025). More accurate public communication, together with strategies to counter the sensationalism encouraged by executive rhetoric and commercial marketing, is therefore essential. A credible educational response requires honesty about harms, participatory policy design, and a clear rejection of techno-solutionist narratives that frame AI as a replacement for teachers, learners, or human judgment. In education, AI must be used to support human learning and expertise, not to legitimise their erosion.

This is also where the broader brain-aligned vision matters. Although frameworks such as Gordon's and LeCun's were not developed specifically for education, their shared emphasis on complementing rather than replacing human intelligence offers a more constructive basis for public engagement than narratives of frictionless automation.

6. Looking Ahead

The near future of AI is likely to involve hybrid systems that combine language models with retrieval, multimodal input, and elements of world modelling (Gordon et al., 2026; LeCun, 2022). If so, the central educational question will sharpen, not weaken: will these systems strengthen the conditions for attention, memory, reasoning, and self-regulation, or hollow them out through convenience?

Progress in AI should therefore be assessed alongside progress in human learning. The most important measure is not whether machines become more fluent, but whether institutions can integrate them in ways that preserve human agency, support cognitive development, and keep education focused on the growth of minds rather than on the outsourcing of thought.

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